

The Effect Of Repentance On Criminal Responsibility From The Perspective Of Islamic Law

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Abstract

The institution of repentance, which is the most desirable mechanism based on the knowledge, remorse and will of the offender in order to achieve the most important goals of criminal law, namely reform and rehabilitation, is one of the causes of the fall of punishment in Islamic criminal law.

The validity of repentance, except for the limit of moharebeh, is limited to its realization before proving the crime, but in ta'zir crimes, repentance is effective at any time and at any stage of the formal proceedings. Despite the criticism, repentance has been accepted even by a rapist.

Relying on the institution of repentance is free from any strictness, and includes all criminals; Provided that it corresponds to reality.

Introduction

Doubts about the effectiveness of repressive criminal responses, along with the emphasis on the protection of human dignity, have led to the prediction of review facilities in religious legal systems, including the involvement of the offender in voluntary adaptation and reform; Which is based on raising his awareness and perception of the deteriorating nature of criminal behavior.

Although punitiveness or justice, as well as repairing and compensating for the damage and damages caused by crime, especially in human rights, are considered as the interests and goals of criminal law, but in many cases, the main purpose of adopting criminal responses is to detain the perpetrator. It is in the light of criminal acts that measures reduce the dangerous capacity and talent of deviants and correct their behavior.

Obviously, the voluntary actions of criminals are the closest and most appropriate way to achieve these goals. Because the effect of such actions, because it is based on the deliberate will of the offender, has a deeper and more lasting strength and influence than the role of the usual reactions of official authorities to the offender.

On the other hand, criminal behavior, especially when the perpetrator adheres to human values and moral restraints, often leads to mental disorder and peace of mind, followed by anxiety and distress of the offender.

The desire to repair the effects of crime and the restoration of peace and tranquility sometimes encourages the perpetrator to confess to the crime in order to expose himself to punishment and to bear the peace of his conscience by enduring it. Otherwise, despair of the possibility of voluntary reconciliation, when accompanied by a natural desire to escape punishment, leads to a situation in which the offender finds it impossible to get rid of the effects of the criminal situation. The idea that his moral conscience has deteriorated leads the criminal to move further away from social norms and values and closer to him. Because he despairs of the possibility of compensating for the effects of the crime, he considers the opportunity to get rid of the swamp of sin and delinquency to be ruled out, and the only way to achieve peace is to accept the unfavorable conditions in which he finds himself. The peace that is established by the wavering of the moral conscience and by accepting the label of delinquency, strengthens his criminal tendencies.

In the Islamic legal system, the restoration of the psychological effects of criminal approaches to relying on punishment is not limited to voluntary adaptation of the offender as a method prior to the application of criminal reactions. Society itself has criminalized the description and considered it a major crime. Accordingly, no factor has prevented the acceptance and effect of voluntary repentance and restoration of the offender's peace of mind, and this has aroused the surprise of Imam Ali (as) from a person who is still restless, disappointed and hopeless despite the possibility of repentance and return to goodness. (Imam Ali (AS), Nahj al-Balaghah, Wisdom 87)

The Holy Qur'an as well as narrative sources repeatedly forbid the criminals from despair and hopelessness about their reunion and harmony with society and divine values, and emphatically promise to accept their remorse and repentance (Zumar / 55).

The legislator has emphasized the importance of this important institution in the Islamic Penal Code adopted in 1392 and in Articles 114 to 119 has considered the repentance of the offender to fall within the limits of punishment, but about the effect of repentance in ta'zir crimes in an unprecedented approach in criminal

jurisprudence He has elaborated on such crimes in such a way that he considered repentance in the first to fifth degree punishments as an optional mitigation of punishment, and in the sixth, seventh and eighth degree punishments, such as hudud, he considered repentance as a reaction.

2- The pillars of repentance

Repentance is a change in the path of life and correction of the individual and social behavior of the offender, which is achieved by his voluntary return to purity and the determination to avoid ugliness.

Repentance is a rising form that, following the "repentance" resulting from "knowledge" of the ugliness of past behavior, evokes the "determination" of the offender to avoid crime in the future. Hence, the pillars of repentance are unique in these three components: knowledge, repentance, and determination. However, some have considered "repentance" as the only pillar of repentance and have achieved this pillar in its realization. Some have considered the emergence of goodness in repentant behavior not as the effect of repentance and its reason, but as the fourth pillar in proving repentance, and have considered it as an essential component in the validity and validity of repentance. According to this group, repentance is a heart and esoteric thing that cannot be achieved unless it occurs in a proper practice. As God Almighty has said, "except those who repented after that and were reformed" (Al-Imran / 89), which the appearance of the verse indicates the lack of repentance without the manifestation of good in the action and behavior of the criminal. (See Shahid I, Bit, vol. 1, p. 436 - Fazel Hindi, 2012, vol. 2, pp. 192-191 - Mawardi, Bit, p. 64)

In emphasizing the need for corrective action in proving repentance, some groups have gone so far as to consider repentance as the same change in behavior, defining it as turning ugly behaviors into good deeds and behaviors. (Rak al-Ghazali, Revival of the Sciences of Religion, vol. 4, p. 40)

While elaborating on the crimes, some believe that in realizing repentance in the rights of God Almighty, repentance and determination not to repeat themselves are enough. But if the crime is a human right, it is a condition that after remorse, he conveys the right to its owner, and if he cannot decide on it until the time of authority; And if he has misled people, his repentance is their guidance. (Ref. Khawaja NasruddinTusi, 1389, pp. 589-588, Abi Al-Salah Halabi, Bit, pp. 243-242, Mohammad Hassan Najafi, 1363, vol. 41, p. 111)

The fact is that repentance is an esoteric matter. Therefore, proper deeds as well as preparation and compensation for damages resulting from the former criminal behavior are not the pillars of repentance but its effects and the reason for the realization of repentance and the honesty of the offender in expressing it and it is not unlikely that these actions indicate perfection of repentance. (Holy Ardabili, Bit, p. 694). Because the above actions are directly independent of the obligatory repentance, so repentance without them is also valid. (Mohammad Hassan Najafi, 1363, vol. 41, p. 113) Therefore, the pillars of repentance are limited to the three components of knowledge, remorse and determination.

1-2- Knowledge

The basic condition in voluntary reform and adaptation is belief in the value system and human norms and the offender's awareness of the ugliness of the perpetrated behavior. Stability will not be on the water; Because turning away from "crime" stems from the intense disgust that is the product of "knowledge" of its ugliness. Just as benevolence is the result of an enthusiasm that dies in the human being in the light of "consciousness."

Therefore, the first step in this process is "knowledge" (Sheikh Baha'i, Bit, p. 237) and therefore some have considered the principle of repentance as the light of knowledge of faith (Ghazali, 1319, p. 756) because this knowledge causes a person to pay attention to the magnitude of the crime and its degree of deterioration leads to heartache, regret and remorse of the offender (FeyzKashani, 1403, vol. 7, p. 5).

Some have considered this knowledge as the power of faith and the light of certainty, because believing in divine values and paying attention to the effects of crime is a crime that ignites the sparks of remorse in his heart and afflicts the former deviation; And it is obvious that the emergence of this state is not possible in disbelief and weakness of faith. (Mullah Ahmad Naraghi, Bit, pp. 500-499)

In fact, it is this knowledge about the ugliness and harmfulness of crime that causes the effective ground for avoiding delinquency and also the effectiveness of criminal reactions, because the faltering of the value system and mitigation of the ugliness of crime in the delinquent mind is the biggest cause of failure of criminal measures.

2-2- Repentance

Repentance in the process of correction and modernization of the offender has such a situation that some have limited repentance to remorse, have considered knowledge as the introduction and determination as the fruit of remorse, and not one of the necessary components and pillars in achieving repentance; (See Sheikh Baha'i, Bit, p. 237, Qazi Abdul Jabbar, 1385, vol. 14, p. 344 and later) because the concept of remorse is reserved for both parties, that is, its fruitfulness, because the breath is empty of knowledge and knowledge that causes it And the determination that seeks it will not be. (FeyzKashani, 1403, vol. 7, p. 5)

The emergence of repentance is not possible except through the decline of the passion of the crime, because if the offender still believes in the usefulness of the crime and cultivates in it a pleasant memory resulting from it, how can he repent of the illusory pleasure of the grieving person and the desire to commit the crime again? Take away your heart.

Al-Ghazali has said in this regard: "Know that the principle of repentance is remorse and the result is a will that arises: But remorse is a sign that it has been enduring, in sorrow and regret, what, whoever sees himself on the verge of destruction, from How can sorrow and grief be empty ... So if there is no fear and sorrow from this, it was that faith has not yet emerged from the plague of sin ..." (Ghazali, 1319, p. 766)

3-2- Determination and will

Voluntary return is the result of a profound change in the delinquent's attitudes and inner desires. A development based on awareness and knowledge that is the source of determination to avoid ugliness and the desire for good. As they have said: "The soul of repentance of repentance and its principle is the light of knowledge of faith and its branch is to change the situation and to quote the situation and organs from sin and opposition to consent and obedience." (Ghazali, 1319, p. 756)

Therefore, repentance is the will of maturity and prosperity, because repentance is not achieved simply by not committing a crime and avoiding it, but it is preventing the soul from turning to ugliness in order to achieve pure purity and spiritual perfection. (Bojnourdi, Seyed Mohammad Hassan, 1419, vol. 7 P. 355)

3- The time of repentance

The limits of the role of repentance in criminal reactions, regardless of the time of its expression or realization, are affected by the time of its proof, because the offender's repentance after committing a crime, before formal prosecutions and at any stage of police prosecution or judicial proceedings can have different effects on punishment. Have committed a crime.

1-3- Urgency of repentance:

Voluntary adaptation is a criminal offense whose obligation is based on religious sources (MuqaddasArdabili, Bitā, p. 694 - Mousavi Bojnourdi, Seyyed Hassan, 1419, vol. 7, p. 327) and the consensus of Islamic jurists (cf. Mullah Ahmad Naraqi, Bitā, p. 501 - Ibn Hazm, Bitā, vol. 11, p. 140) and rational signification (cf. Judge Abdul Jabbar, 1385, vol. 14, p. 335) is constant.

The obligation to repent is immediate and the offender is obliged to act immediately after committing the crime and without delay. (FeyzKashani, Mullah Mohsen, 1403, vol. 7, p140)

The urgency of the obligation of repentance, in addition to the religious arguments, is based on the rule of reason. This and the delay in repentance, in some opinions, have been described as criminal, they have considered it as a kind of insistence on delinquency (cf. Jorjani, Bitā, p. 32).

Accordingly, inviting the offender to repentance has been considered as a rational and religious duty by the official police and judicial authorities, as well as each member of society, because this action is a call through wisdom and truth that at any time, even after the verdict is issued. Execution of punishment is also considered necessary (Ibn Hazm, vol. 11, p. 140).

2-3- Repentance before proof

The effect of repentance on the fall of punishment, at any stage of the prosecution and preparation and completion of the case in law enforcement agencies and the prosecutor's office (Sheikh Tusi, Bitā, vol. 8 p. 40 - Sarakhsi, 1406, vol. 9 p. 176 - Sheikh Abi al-Salah Halabi, Bitā, Pp. 407 and 412 - Jaziri, Abdul Rahman, Bitā, vol. 5, pp. 207-206 - Mohammad Hassan Najafi, 1363, vol. 41, p. 308) and the court (Sheikh Abi Salah Halabi, pp. 413-409-407 - Imam Khomeini, Bitā, Vol. 2, p. 481 - Mohammad Hassan Najafi, 1363, Vol. The degree of severity of the crime committed, doubt in the honesty of the offender after conquering him, prevents the acceptance of repentance (Mohammad Hassan Najafi, 1363, vol. 41, pp. 581 - 526 - Shahid Thani, 1416, vol. 2, p. 427 - Ibn Hazm, Bitā, Vol. 11 p. 124- Ibn Qadameh, Bitā, vol. 10, p. 315 - Al-Ramli, Bitā, vol. 8, p. 6).

Some Islamic jurists have considered the expression of repentance after referring the case to the court and raising the issue with the judge as ineffective (Al-Qurtabi, 1387, vol. 6, p. 7 - Ibn Hazm, Bitā, vol. 11, p. 130 - Mohi-ud-Din Arabi, 1981, p. 402). However, following the famous quote in Article 114 of the Islamic Penal Code, the legislator accepts the repentance of the perpetrator of certain crimes - except moharebeh - before the crime is proven, and in Note 1 of this article, he states: The limit is falling.

Therefore, expressing repentance after proving a certain crime and before or during the punishment of Muscat will not be unless the crime has been proven by confession (Fazel Hindi, 2012, vol. 2, p. 215 - Mohammad Hassan Najafi, 1363, vol. 41, p. 526 - Imam Khomeini, Bitā, vol. 2, p. 481). In this case, by repenting, the perpetrator can request amnesty from the Supreme Leader by the head of the judiciary. In this case, with the possibility of confessing the former repentance and also considering the limits of public awareness of the crime and its reputation, and especially in terms of the purpose of intimidation and threatening severe punishments, the ruler of the Islamic society at the request of the judge, Forgives.

Proof of guilt is obviously the criterion of validity in the court of first instance. However, if the offender's repentance has not been considered in the trial court - whether the offense has been proven by confession or other evidence, such as evidence - the offender can provide reasons for his repentance, as the case may be, before the verdict is final. Prove the crime after the confession of the offender and prove the crime) to submit to the prosecuting authority or the court of appeal.

3-3- Repentance after proof

As the passing of the offender's repentance in the crimes of hadd after the proof of the crime will not invalidate the hadd, however, if the hadd is proved by confession, repentance can be considered as a reason for pardon of the offender.

Some, while emphasizing the similarity of the rules of repentance in hadd and ta'zir, have extended the restrictions on accepting repentance in hadd to ta'zir to believe that if the perpetrator repents after proving the ta'zir crime, it will not affect the fall of punishment (Ibn Najim, 1986, p. 218) The appearance of the words of some jurists also tends to this view (Sheikh Tusi, Al-Nahaya, Bita, p. 714) (and also Ibn Idris, 1411, vol. 3, p. 478, Sheikh Abi Al-Salah Halabi, Bita, p. 77).

The supporting reasons for this opinion have been considered as the application of hadd to ta'zir in some narrations, and therefore they have considered the rulings of ta'zir as subject to hudud. Unless a specific reason has excluded the case, because in the language of narrations there is often a limit including ta'zir. (Mohammad Hassan Najafi, 1363, vol. 41, p. 257)

However, since the main purpose of imposing ta'zir reactions is to correct and educate the offender, if he achieves this goal at any stage of the proceedings by voluntary correction and adaptation, the execution of punishment or the continuation of ta'zir punishment is useless and expedient. Therefore, as soon as repentance is committed in ta'zir crimes, the imposition of punishment is unjustified and the punishment is abolished. For this reason, many Islamic jurists, including the distinction of crimes subject to the hadd punishment of ta'zir, have mentioned the absolute possibility - the acceptance of repentance in ta'zir - contrary to the limitations that exist (Allameh Majlisi Mohammad Baqir, Bita, p. 59) (Qarafi, vol. 4, p. 181)

In addition, many documents indicate the effect of repentance during the execution of ta'zir punishment and the cessation of its continuation, including the cessation of imprisonment of a criminal who has been convicted of committing the crime of moharebeh and has repented while serving his sentence (Abdullah bin Maudood, 1980p114); Repentance of a person who is in prison on charges of evil (Sarakhsi, vol. 24, p. 36). And also, a person who has been sentenced to imprisonment for taking usury and repents while serving his sentence. (Sheikh Mufid, 1410, p. 801)

In some cases, the legislature has accepted the suspension of punishment, even in certain crimes, as soon as it is repented, as stated in Article 284 of the Islamic Penal Code: "If he does not repent, he will remain in exile."

In some cases, the repentance of the offender during the execution of the sentence is considered as one of the reasons for the ruling to change the amnesty or commutation and change his punishment. 2 states: "Regarding paragraph (c) of this article and other imprisonments that are not subject to the title of ta'zir, if the perpetrator repents while serving the sentence and the position of the Supreme Leader deems it expedient, he will be released from imprisonment with his pardon." "Also, the Supreme Leader can change his punishment to another ta'zir punishment."

Therefore, repentance may sometimes affect the execution of a punishment, and in the first way this effect is more justified in ta'zir, especially since the permission of ta'zir depends on its usefulness and expediency, and after the repentance of the offender, in performing ta'zir There is no conceivable interest in correcting him. Prosecution and execution of punishment must be stopped whenever the offender repents.

Application of Article 115 of the Islamic Penal Code, on the other hand, while developing the role of repentance in ta'zir crimes, has considered its occurrence at any time and at any stage of the formal investigation process as valid and effective. Therefore, in the sixth, seventh and eighth degree ta'zir crimes, the repentance of the offender before or after the proof of the crime and in the stages of preliminary prosecution, or trial and after the issuance of the sentence and during the execution of the sentence, will cause a reaction.

However, the legislature sometimes, in cases where the nature of the offense is a type of some offense. Restrictions on the role of repentance in the fall of punishment have also been extended to ta'zir. As in the note of Article 512 of the Penal Code on crimes against internal and external security, the effect of repentance, like its role in Modaraba, is subject to its attainment before the arrest of the offender.

This approach has also been followed with regard to the punishment of perpetrators of crimes of preparing and promoting heart coins, as provided in the last part of Article 521 of the said law: "They will be exempted."

4- Discrimination of repentance

In cases where the expression of repentance implies the remorse of the offender for past criminal acts, and his determination to avoid any crime in the future, the slightest doubt in accepting the repentance of the offender is eliminated. However, if the offender binds his repentance to specific crimes with relative correction and remorse, so that his statements are explicitly or implicitly such that he has limited his repentance to a number of crimes by discriminating between them, about the possibility The occurrence of repentance as mentioned above and its validity and accuracy have been disputed in such a way that some groups have ruled out the possibility of discrimination in repentance and some have commented on its validity.

1-4- Impossibility of discrimination

Some have considered discrimination in repentance as detrimental to its proof, and repentance of some crimes, but not all of them, have been considered possible and correct.

Therefore, the verdict, if the perpetrator of border theft expresses remorse before proving the crime and states in his repentance that he will never commit the crime of border theft after this. If the court finds his repentance and his serious determination on this matter, but his non-repentance from committing other criminal acts such as crimes against chastity, drinking alcohol or even ta'zir theft, it is certain that his repentance to the theft is ineffective to some extent. Muscat will not be punished.

And so it is whenever a person repents after committing drinking alcohol and it is proved that he has seriously avoided committing the crime during the period provided for his repentance and the emergence of behavior that confirms his sincerity in expressing repentance, but in committing other crimes, such as violating the financial rights of others, has been reckless. His repentance is not limited to drinking alcohol. According to this group, committing crimes other than drinking alcohol prevents him from repenting, eliminating the possibility of falling into the punishment of drinking alcohol, because discrimination against repentance is neither possible nor correct, because the truth of repentance is repentance. The remorse that comes from knowing the ugliness of criminal behavior. So, what causes the regret and remorse of repentance is the dissatisfaction of God in performing the behavior and the ugliness of that action. And this feature, which is the basis of his remorse, is common to all crimes, regardless of their title, that is, repentance is a cause that is a characteristic of delinquency, so because due to remorse, all crimes are common. Others are impossible and unjustified.

In other words, when the offender's intention to avoid the crime stems from the remorse arising from his knowledge of the ugliness of the crime in the eyes of the Shari'a, the specific title of criminal behavior has no effect on this remorse because of the nature of the ugly nature of the act and it is present in all crimes, and therefore all criminal acts are the same. Repentance from a reprehensible thing, therefore, will not be possible and valid because it is reprehensible - despite the desire for another reprehensible.

Thus, in this theory, true repentance of a crime requires the renunciation of all crimes, because the truth of repentance is the return from divine opposition and return to legalism and discipline in individual and social behavior, and by adhering to some values and abandoning others, Repentance is not possible because repentance from a crime such as theft is because it is a crime, not because of the characteristic that distinguishes it from other crimes as theft. In other words, repentance from theft is not because it is theft but because of rebellion. Being and being a crime, so because all crimes are shared due to remorse and determination to leave, repenting of stealing without remorse for adultery or disgust with drinking alcohol is unreasonable because they are all sins and in terms of being a crime. They have a single nature. Therefore, in spite of the unity of motive in repentance, which is the knowledge of the abomination that is present in all crimes, the intention arising from repentance must also belong to all crimes, and any separation and discrimination in repentance will disturb the proof and prevent its attainment (Al-Qazwini, 1422, p. 458)

2-4- Possibility of discrimination

Most Islamic writers have considered the discrimination of repentance as possible and correct. (Tabatabai, Seyyed Mohammad Kazem, *Bitā*, vol. 2, p. 304-Najafi, Sheikh Mohammad Hassan, 1363, vol. 41, p. 113) Repent of the offense strongly against the Shari'a or because of the severe punishment imposed on a particular offense, but do not repent for minor offenses that are amnestiable, or only express remorse for offenses to which they are less inclined.

Hence, repentance from the big and not the minor, repentance from murder and not persecution of others, repentance from drinking alcohol and not encroachment on other people's property, etc. are possible. Rather, most of the repentances that are stated are like this, but in these cases, of course, the repentance of the offender will be effective only in relation to the punishment of the crime from which he has repented.

Some have relied on this narration to strengthen their claim that repentance is possible and correct, saying: "The one who repents of his sins is the one who does not commit sins" and did not say that the one who repents of his sins (Naraqī, Mohammad Mehdi, *Bitā*, vol. 3, p. 63)

Therefore, the basis for the determination to avoid crime may be different and the motivation of the offender to repent of certain crimes may be the severity and weakness of the ugliness of the crimes or the extent of their punishment, or the extent of his desires and interests and the like. The distinction of repentance is justified, and the correctness of the thief's repentance cannot be questioned, for example because of his drug addiction, because the offender's repentance can avoid crimes that are usually avoided due to intense desire or addiction to do so. It is accompanied by difficulty, to give up. Therefore, it is unreasonable to make a repentant subject to quitting his addiction and crimes like that. In addition, the non-acceptance of the validity of the discrimination of repentance limits the possibility of benefiting from the institution of repentance to accidental criminals, intellectuals and divine guardians, while the evidence of repentance implies inviting all criminals and accepting their repentance.

In view of the above, some have considered the promise of impossibility as well as the impermissibility and correctness of discrimination in repentance as extremely weak, have considered its occurrence as a reason for its possibility, and as the basis of the possibility and correctness of discrimination in repentance have been considered differences. In crimes (in terms of degree of ugliness), and in punishments (in terms of severity) and

the characteristics of penitent offenders (in terms of type of interests and inclinations) there is (Bojnourdi, Mohammad Hassan, 1419, vol. 7, p. 344)

3-4- The criterion of discrimination

Although the discrimination of repentance and its validity is justified and defensible, but the absolute acceptance of discrimination and validity of any form of distinction between crimes is unreasonable because repentance from stealing houses and not stealing cars or repentance of a certain type of alcohol and ... unjustifiable. Hence, they have made the possibility and validity of discrimination conditional on restrictions, some of which relate it to the mental and psychological aspects, and some to the material aspect of the crimes from which they have repented.

1-3-4- Objective criteria

The most important condition for the correctness of the discrimination of repentance is the non-similarity of some crimes. Therefore, if the type of crimes for which the offender has repented is the same as the type of crimes to which repentance has not been attributed, discrimination of repentance is not possible, but repentance from theft is possible and correct without repentance from drinking alcohol. Therefore, repentance from a certain kind of theft and not absolute theft, or repentance from a form of adultery or some kind of wine is unacceptable.

Criteria in different types of crimes may be different. According to some, this criterion can be related to differences in crimes in terms of severity and weakness of punishment, so that the cause of the offender's determination to leave the crime, the wrath of God or severe punishment in some crimes (Bojnourdi, Mohammad Hassan, 1419, vol. 7, p. 344) In this case, repentance from the big and not the small, etc. is permissible, as if the criminal repents from stealing to some extent. Without intending to avoid ta'zirtheft!!!

The criterion for the non-similarity of the crimes from which the offender has repented may be the type of crimes in terms of their material nature and gender, regardless of the severity and weakness of the punishment or the judicial nature of the crime, in which case repentance from adultery The opposite of chastity will be like sodomy and tafkhiz and the like. Because it is not possible to discriminate between the sexes and their nature, even if the punishment of some is hadd and others are ta'zir.

2-3-4- Mental criteria

Another criterion in discrimination of crimes is the motive and purpose of the offender in committing them. In this case, the possibility of repentance from theft without repentance is derived from fraud because although the two crimes are materially different from each other, the motive in both cases is benefit. Illegal is through the possession of another's property. Hence, in crimes against property in which the motive and purpose of the offender is the seizure of another's property, or in crimes against chastity in which the plaintiff has sexual pleasure, repentance is non-discriminatory and the offender cannot distinguish between all kinds of crimes against property and ownership. Repent in a certain way or repent of sodomy and not adultery or incitement.

According to the mentioned criterion, it does not require the material nature of the type of crime in all cases. He repents but has not repented of other forms of aggression and persecution.

According to this ruling, the condition for non-similarity of crimes in the license to repent discrimination is the difference between the desires and motives of the offender in committing the crime. And it's right.

4-4- Discrimination against repentance in the Islamic Penal Code

The Islamic Penal Code of 1392 is silent about the possibility of discrimination in repentance, but some evidence indicates the similarity and the same number of severe penal offenses with the legislator, which can be considered as a parallel to the inaccuracy of repentance discrimination in punishments. For example, the acceptance of general repetition in ta'zir crimes under Article 137, in addition to indicating the similarity and non-difference of ta'zir crimes in this case, confirms that the purpose of a taazi conviction or the application of such reactions is to correct the offender in such a way that He should avoid not only the crime for which he has been sentenced, but also all the first to sixth degree crimes.

In addition, the emphasis on the similarity of ta'zir crimes is reflected in the provisions on multiplicity in such crimes. In Article 134 of the Islamic Penal Code, the legislator has considered the first to sixth degree ta'zir crimes to be the same regardless of their differences in the type of crime, the amount and type of punishment, or the motive and the perpetrator.

Therefore, the opinion of all ta'zir crimes is the same for the legislator, and for this reason, it is impossible to accept the discrimination of repentance, because the validity of the discrimination of repentance depends on the reality of discrimination and discrimination of crimes, which eliminates the possibility of discrimination.

In addition, since repentance actually achieves the goal of ta'zir reactions through a different mechanism, so that the effects of repentance replace the effects of taazir, repentance must cause the same form of correction that is desired in the execution of ta'zir, but also deeper and wider. The effect of repentance should never be less than the effect of ta'zir.

Therefore, if ta'zir, according to the legislator, should lead to the correction of the offender and his avoidance of all ta'zir crimes, then repentance, which is Muscat ta'zir, should achieve the same goal in the first way. Repentance from a crime is also considered as repentance from all ta'zir crimes.

The legislator has considered the criterion in the similarity of limit crimes as different from ta'zir crimes, and has considered the two criteria of gender unity and uniformity of punishment necessary to achieve the similarity of limit crimes. As stated in Article 132 of the Islamic Penal Code on the multiplicity of limits: "In crimes that cause hadd, the multiplicity of crimes leads to the multiplicity of punishments, except in cases where the crimes committed and their punishment are the same."

Therefore, the unity of the claimant and the motive does not cause the similarity of limit crimes, but in addition to the similarity of the type of crime, the similarity of gender and the amount of punishment is also a condition. In other words, committing adultery causes a different cover from the crime of adultery causing stoning. However, in these two crimes, the perpetrator and the type of crime are the same. However, due to differences in punishment, they are considered two different crimes.

Therefore, in some crimes, unlike punishments, discrimination in repentance is possible and correct. In such a way that the thief can repent of the crime of theft and not adultery, in addition to tolerance in the limits and based on mitigation has caused a special type of adultery that has a different punishment from other forms is considered unlike other types of adultery, discrimination in repentance Adultery should be accepted in one way and not absolutely.

The mentioned criteria in discriminating crimes do not apply in cases where two crimes are different from the two categories. For example, the two crimes of hadd and ta'zir are considered the same when they are of the same sex, despite their differences in type and amount of punishment. However, if both are within the limits, they are not considered similar due to the difference in punishment.

Therefore, repentance from border theft includes ta'zir theft, and although discrimination of repentance is possible in all types of adultery, discrimination of repentance from adultery and illegitimate relationships is less than adultery.

Therefore, in hadd crimes, the offender can only repent of some hadd crimes and not others, even if they are of the same sex. However, in ta'zir crimes, it is not possible to discriminate against repentance, because according to the legislator's approach, ta'zir crimes are considered as first to sixth degree similar crimes, and apparently the purpose of repentance, like the purpose of ta'zir for each of these crimes, is to avoid all those crimes.

By separating and categorizing ta'zir crimes, the legislator has accepted discrimination between first to sixth degree crimes on the one hand and seventh- and eighth-degree crimes on the other hand. That is, the offender can repent of only one of these two groups in ta'zir and not of all ta'zir crimes.

The above-mentioned interpretation of the legal material somehow requires strictness in accepting repentance in punishments and neglecting the degree of correction and education of the offender, and especially because it ignores the differences in the principles of the criminals in their correction and their different motives and drugs in committing the crime. It is indefensible.

While remorse, which is motivated by the desire to commit a particular crime and is accompanied by a determination to avoid that crime, when it is based on the knowledge of the offender about the ugliness of the crime, is an example of repentance because the absolute decline of sin is specific to intellectuals and saints. It is specific to God that there is no condition for accepting repentance.

Therefore, accepting the possibility of discrimination, repentance and its correctness in punishments is valid, but the condition for the possibility of discrimination is the non-similarity of crimes, and the criterion in this is the difference of some crimes, especially differences in motives, because what leads a person to commit a crime His desire is for illegitimate gain. The truth of repentance is the transformation of this desire into disgust and hatred, so turning the external face of illegitimate interests from one type to another is never considered repentance.

5- Result

The institution of repentance in Islamic criminal policy is one of the most effective mechanisms based on a corrective approach against crime, because the participation and support of the offender in his adaptation and education in the pursuit of knowledge and knowledge of the nature of the crime, the most lasting educational effect based on the will of the offender.

The realization of repentance depends on the attainment of the three pillars of knowledge, repentance and determination, so that the absence of any of them prevents the proof of repentance. Therefore, if repentance does not come from knowledge, although it may be considered as mitigation, its attainment alone is not considered repentance, just as the offender's intention to avoid delinquency does not make him enjoy the effects of repentance when his will does not come from remorse.

Although the legislator in the past sporadically mentioned the effect of repentance in punishment in some crimes and some punishments, but the Islamic Penal Code of 1392 has brought the rules governing this institution in general in the first book.

According to this law, the repentance of the offender is a punishment until certain crimes are proven, but the legislator has neglected to specify the time of valid repentance in ta'zir crimes, although ta'zir arguments and emphasis on correcting the offender as the most important goal of ta'zir reactions, and the application of the relevant materials also indicates the acceptance of repentance at any stage of the proceedings or execution of ta'zir.

By deviating from the Shari'a norms, while legislating between ta'zir crimes, the legislator has considered repentance in the sixth, seventh- and eighth-degree punishments as the cause of the reaction. And in other ta'zir crimes, repentance is considered ineffective and its role is sometimes weaker than the offender's remorse and as one of the voluntary aspects of mitigation. Although his repentance was stated before his arrest and proof of guilt.

Discrimination in repentance is possible; And the remorse of the offender only for some crimes will not prevent its validity. Therefore, if the crimes are not similar in terms of type and especially the offender in committing them, the relative remorse and case correction of the offender with repentance and determination to avoid some crimes is also correct and causes the punishment to fall.

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